

Impact of Habitat Destruction on Livelihoods and Vulnerability of Forest Dependent Communities in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract: *Wildlife diversity has been reported to be dependent on quality of the environment. However, information on wildlife species within Bonny Island forest has not been adequately documented. In fragile ecosystems such as Bonny Island, the lakes, vegetation, wildlife, and freshwater condition are very valuable especially to the indigenous people. Thus, the socio-economic factors in respect to the consequent effect of wildlife destruction were determined. Structured questionnaire was used to collect information from respondents using systematic sampling techniques in Bonny Satellite Settlement (BSS) and Bonny Island Settlement (BIS). Data were analyzed using simple percentage. Anthropogenic activities: hunting, fishing and other agricultural practices exerted higher pressure of 20.0%, 60.0% and 10.0% respectively on the wildlife resources during dry than wet seasons (17.5%, 43.8% and 38.70% respectively). These however place the communities at a very vulnerable condition because it affected their access to land, protein source and other non timber forest product. Anthropogenic activities were threats to wildlife diversity and the local communities. If biodiversity is lost, the poor rural people will be heavily affected hence measures on conservation and should be put in place and also community participation should be encouraged. Public enlightenment on conservation of natural resources in Bonny Island should be encouraged.*
Keywords: *Vulnerability, Livelihoods, Habitat Destruction, Forest Dependent Communities*

INTRODUCTION

Niger Delta's freshwater swamp forest covers some 12000 km² or about half of the delta (NDES, 1997) and one third of Rivers State. The forest is either partially or wholly flooded throughout the year (Agbagwa, 2008). Mounds and ridges on the ground of this forest form numerous intricate narrow channels through which flood circulate on the forest floor. These channels also provide drainage network from the forest to surrounding rivers and streams, thus regulating coastal water flow and elimination of silt, sediment and pollutants from moving water (Asthana and Asthana, 2003). They are variable in size, form and plant community structure (Chapman and Reiss, 1995). The freshwater swamp forest is one of the most productive ecosystems of the world. In the Niger Delta, it is a store house of biological diversity providing suitable habitats for plants (Omokhua and Koyejo, 2008), important areas for rare and endangered wildlife and enormous benefits to the people.

With the astronomical deforestation of the other forest zones in Nigeria, the freshwater swamp forest remained the most extensive forest zone due largely to the swampy ground on which they exist which hitherto hindered exploitation. However, the continued existence of this forest in the region is seriously threatened by the ingress of sea water through canalization to facilitate oil and gas activities (Agbagwa and Akpokodje, 2010), expansion of agriculture, fuel wood collection, pole and timber harvesting and urbanization.

The freshwater swamp forest of Bonny Island is currently faced with the aforementioned problems, because as a major hub of oil and gas activities in the Niger Delta where available land space is scarce, industrial expansion resulting in deforestation is expected. For instance, the construction of the Nigerian Liquefied Natural Gas (NLNG) Plant in 1999 required the reclaiming of approximately 2.27 km² of the forest in Finima, Bonny Island. More than this area was also reclaimed for the resettlement of the indigenous Finima people. Thus, it is obvious that this forest ecosystem is gradually being destroyed without proper articulation of its wealth of phyto-diversity.

The depletion of biodiversity, (Flora and Fauna,) destruction and contamination of soil, and the much obvious air/atmospheric pollution in the Niger delta has deteriorated the environment (Ajibade *et al.*, 2009). Deforestation and environmental degradation in Finima-Bonny Island Forest Reserves have accelerated dramatically in recent decades and there is need for more research studies to be directed towards controlling wildlife-diversity loss. The forests are being cut and burned at an alarming rate for agricultural uses and industrial demand from huge palm oil plantations to oil mining and slash or burning for subsistence farming.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Bonny is a town and a Local Government Area in Rivers State, southeastern Nigeria. It is on the Bight of Biafra within Latitude 4°26' 0" N and Longitude 7°10' 0" E. It is approximately 56 km from upland Port Harcourt, the capital city of Rivers State Niger Delta. A small island located just offshore with predominantly freshwater swamp and mangrove forests, Bonny Island, is a major export point for crude oil and gas. The region produces a type of crude oil known as Bonny Light oil. Much of the crude oil extracted onshore in Rivers State is piped to Bonny for export. Due to its strategic position, the island hosts various multi-national oil and gas companies, whose continuous expansion impact directly on the forest ecosystem.

Fig 1: Map of River State showing the study area

DATA COLLECTION

Structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The study area was split into two namely BIs and BSS. The BIs was split into 3 for proper coverage, these include Bonny town, Finima and other communities on the island. The other communities were grouped into 5 following contiguity and proximity

- Group1: Green Iwoma, Banigo village, Dan jumbo and George Pepple
 2: Abalamabie, Dema, Allison, Ishileogono and Otuokolo
 3: Oloma, Georgekiri, Burukiri, Epellema,
 4: Sangama, Ererekiri, Agbalama, Otobie
 5: Oputumbie, Iwokiri, Mumakiri, Egelebie

One hundred and fifty (150) copies of questionnaires were dispensed to other communities as listed above (30 per group), 120 to Bonny town and 80 copies to Finima making a total of 350 structured questionnaires for Bonny Island. The data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

RESULT

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION OF RESPONDENTS

Result reveals that 43.5% of the respondents from Bonny Island have just primary education while those from Finima had 8.7% and other settlements had 47.8%. On the other hand, 77.8% in Bonny Island, 11% in Finima and 11.1% in other settlements possess secondary education certificates respectively. Data on gender reveals that there are 73.3% male and 26.7% female within Bonny Island while finima had 75% male, 25% female. Other communities from the five groups had 60% female and 40% male (figure 1).

Sex Status

Figure 1: Distribution of the Respondents by their Sex Status

Marital Status

Figure 2: Distribution of the Respondents by their Marital Status

Figure 2 shows that 47.5% were single, 50% were married and 2.5% were divorced in Bonny Island while 68.8% were single, 31.3% were married and there was no divorced case in Finima. It also revealed that 57.3% were single, 34.0% were married and 8.7% were divorced outside Bonny Island.

Figure 3: Distribution of the Respondents by their Occupation

Result on occupational status shows that 21.3% of the respondents are engaged in personal occupation (that is, petty traders), 62.5% of the respondents were engaged in private occupation (fishing and farming) and 16.3% were civil servants in Finima. Survey from Bonny Island shows that 25% of the respondents were engaged in personal occupation, 26.7% were engaged in private business while 48.3% were civil servant. Result from other town/villages revealed that 58% were into private business, 26.7% were into personal business while 15.3% were civil servant.

PERCEIVED CAUSES OF HABITAT DEGRADATION AND ITS EFFECT ON THE LOCAL COMMUNITIES

It was revealed from the result that 21.2% of the respondents affirm Government involvement in the destruction of the vegetation, 48.5% of the respondents confirm the involvement of company in the destruction of the vegetation while 30.3% of the respondents affirm the involvement of strangers in the destruction of vegetation in Bonny Island. 25% of the respondents confirm Government involvement in the destruction of the vegetation, 68.6% of the respondents affirm the company involvement in the destruction of the vegetation while 6.23% of the respondents establish strangers involvement in the destruction of vegetation in Bonny satellite settlement (BSS).

100% of the respondents affirm that there was displacement of villages by sea action five years ago while 90.9% of the respondents affirm that the displacement occur 10 years ago in bonny island. 85% of the respondents confirm the displacements of the villages by sea action, 15% of the respondents did not experience displacement of villages by sea action. 75% of the respondents said the displacement occurred five years ago while 37.5% of the respondents said it occurred 10 years ago in BSS.

The villages in bonny island affirm the list of animals they usually see along the shoreline as follows; Alligator, monitor lizard, crocodile, duck, agama lizard, monkey, heron, king fisher etc while the respondents in BSS confirm the common animals they usually see along the shoreline as follows; Crocodile, monitor lizard, otter, antelope, monkey, heron, king fisher, duck, egret, grasscutter, bush dog, water snake. The following animals are visitors in bonny Island while BSS have the following animals as their visitors; Monkey, otter, heron, duck. 39.4% of the respondents affirm the existence of the animals while 60.6% of the respondents affirm the disappearance of the animals in Bonny Island. 62.5% of the respondents confirm the existence of the animals while 37.5% of the respondents affirm the extinction of the animals in BSS.

Also, 93.9% of the respondents affirm observed changes such as flying of insects, frequent birds at night, heating effects, thick release of smoke and dark water collected from rain due to gas flares while only 6.1% of the respondents said they did not observed changes as a result of gas flares in Bonny Island. 79.5% of the respondents affirm changes in the environment such as less time to sleep, Black water from rain and High heat due to gas flares while 11.4% of the respondents said they don't know if there has been a change in BSS.

Based on the perception of the people towards the reserve in the area, 67.5% of the respondents affirm that they will be happy If the reserve was removed or destroyed by any activities owing to the reason that they are not given opportunity to used the reserve; while 32% of the respondents did not subscribed to the destruction of the reserve in bonny island. 86.7% of the respondents agree to the destruction of the reserve while 13.3% of the respondents disagree to the destruction of the reserve in BSS. 70% of the respondents said if given the opportunity, they we kill animal within the reserve while 30% of the respondents disagree to the killing of animals if given the opportunity in bonny island. 92% of the respondents subscribed also to the killing of animals within the reserve while 8% of the respondents did not in BSS.

More so, 99% of the respondents affirm that there has been attack of animal on human being from the reserve while only 1% of the respondents disagrees to those facts in bonny island. 100% of the respondents confirm that there has been attack of animal on human being from the reserve in BSS. 90% of the respondents affirm that they like eating bush meat while 10% of the respondents confirm that they dislike bush meat in Bonny Island.

LEVEL OF COMMUNITIES DEPENDENCE ON THE FOREST

The result depicts that local people as for long depended on the forest for their protein as 60% of the respondents affirm their interest in eating bush meat while 40% of the respondents dislike eating bush meat in BSS. 85.7% of the respondents affirm that they get their bush meat outside the Island while 14.3% of the respondents get theirs from the reserve. 82.4% of the respondent gets their bush meat within the reserve while 17.6% of the respondents did not disclose their source of bush meat in BSS.

The study revealed that the common animals usually used as bush meat in BIs and BSS are; Monkey, Antelope, Grasscutter, Monitor lizard, Python, Squirrel, Tortoise, Bush Dog, Bush Dog, Crocodile, Kite/Eagle. 25% of the respondents obtain fire wood for cooking from the forest, 60% of the respondents affirms that they buy fire wood while 15% of the respondents obtain fire wood from the reserve in Bonny Island. 92% of the respondents obtain their fire wood from the forest while 8% of the respondents buy fire wood in BSS. The study shows that 61.9% of the respondents cut red wood (mangrove) for fire wood while 38.1% of the respondents cut *Lophira alata* for fire wood in Bonny Island.

Seventy five percent of the respondents affirm that if given the opportunity they will appreciate alternative means of cooking while 25% of the respondents did not appreciate alternative means of cooking. 95.5% of the respondents prefer alternative means of cooking while 4.5% of the respondents did not prefer alternative means of cooking. 84.8% of the respondents confirm the creaming off of vegetation for farming purposes while 15.2% of the respondents remove vegetation for building purposes in Bonny Island. 83.8% of the respondents affirm the remover of the vegetation for farming purposes while 16.3% of the respondents remove vegetation for building purposes in BSS.

DISCUSSION

Survey from this study has shown that the local people are majorly dependent on the natural resources. Most of them are engaged in farming, hunting and fishing. Despite the rate of poverty amidst population increase, the people's efforts to achieve economic and ecological sustainability are being severely threatened. It was pointed out from the result that the Bonny Island has been heavily exploited as a result of the presence from massive oil exploration by various companies. This however makes them vulnerable because they are forest dependent people.

This also corroborates with FAO (2014) where it was stated that the livelihoods of biodiversity dependent people are under growing demands and the ecosystem services that the natural environment provides are also under threat. In addition, Freshwater provisions are already long-drawn-out through rising population and industrial demand. These freshwater resources are also being contaminated by salt water and waste water. Coastal lands are undergoing significant salinity changes which are affecting agricultural productivity and other resources which it provides. This local people gets virtually everything they need to maintain a stable livelihood from the forest which include thatch from raffia, protein source (bushmeat or fish), and other non timber forest products. The locals are able to get all these from the forest because the Niger delta forest is blessed with abundant biodiversity.

Many rural families depend on biodiversity for income. This they have overexploited and destroyed leaving very little or nothing to exploit for income to take care of their food, clothing and shelter needs (Agbogidi and Ufuoko, 2006). They fear that they will have to move to another location or face extinction in a land so negatively affected by the oil companies, such that it can no longer support them as it once supported their ancestors. In spite of the area's abundant natural resources, the potential for development remains unfulfilled and threatened by environmental devastation and worsening economic, social, and political conditions.

In addition to the negative impact on local communities' economies, environmental pollution and degradation, and lack of access to assets including basic education, clean water, a diversified economy, and healthcare delivery that hold the keys to unlocking poverty's grip are other forms of human deprivation. Therefore, in the Niger Delta, marginalization and exclusion from the ownership of assets and lack of access to social amenities defines poverty. It is only if and when development strategies address these factors holistically that the possibility of alleviating poverty and reducing vulnerability exists. The programme for addressing rural poverty must identify and target the most vulnerable, and these are the host communities. If the habitat is affected by any means there will be a down turn on the people's way of life because they have a complex relationship with the forest in terms of tradition/customs, herbs from the forest, protein source, employment, and land to farm among other activities and forest benefits.

CONCLUSION

This paper examines the level of dependence of local communities to natural resources and their vulnerability to habitat destruction. The study reveals that the dependency of the communities on the forest for livelihood is very high despite the great loss of habitat from anthropogenic activities like the oil exploration. The local people are the most vulnerable from all stances because their survival depends on the status quo of the forest.

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